

PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY OF DIGITAL CRYPTOCURRENCY ASSET INVESTMENT IN INDONESIA BASED ON CURRENT LAW RUPIAH MONEY AND ECONOMIC THEORY OF REGULATION WITH COMPARATION OF TAX COLLECTION RULES AND IMPLEMENTATION OF QANUN SYARI'AH

Rico Nur Ilham ^{1*}, Dr. Henry Aspan ² and Siti Nurhayati ³

¹ Universitas Malikussaleh, Indonesia.

^{1,2,3} Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Medan, Indonesia.

*Corresponding Author Email: riconurilham@unimal.ac.id

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.12605018](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12605018)

Abstract

This research aims to describe Phenomenological Study of Cryptocurrency Digital Asset Investment in Indonesia in Comparison of Tax Collection Rules and Implementation of Sharia Qanun. Literature review or literature review is a method used in research research. The research method in this study uses normative juridical research methods. The data collection technique used is library research. Data obtained during the research will be analyzed using qualitative descriptive methods. Crypto research results aside from being a transaction tool, crypto is also popular with the public as an investment. One aspect of taxation imposed on crypto assets is Value Added Tax (VAT) and PPh. Views of Islamic economic law and Sharia Qanun So several findings can be outlined, including: As a digital financial transaction system, cryptocurrency basically uses relatively new technology, the nature of its legality still needs to be studied in more depth, but it is not a form of violation. In Indonesia itself, the government has not taken a definite stance on the existence of cryptocurrency, so people are still allowed to use it. However, investing in cryptocurrency carries a very high risk because its value can rise or fall drastically and unpredictably.

Keywords: *Cryptocurrencies, Tax Collection Rules and Implementation of Qanun Syari'ah.*

A. INTRODUCTION

Discussions about cryptocurrency have become a subject that has received increasing attention in recent years in Indonesia. As popularity continues to grow, the question of how cryptocurrencies are treated from a tax law perspective is becoming increasingly important. In this context, the jurisdiction of Indonesian tax law regarding cryptocurrencies is the subject of extensive debate and research. An introduction to cryptocurrencies and related tax regulations in Indonesia is an important first step for anyone interested in understanding and getting involved in the world of digital currencies. Cryptocurrency is not a legal have in mind of expenditure in Indonesia. This is in conformation with the modifications stipulated in collection character 7 of 2011 in reference to Currency. on the authority of these up-to-dateness regulations, the Rupiah is a up-to-dateness created by the asian sovereign state and is a permissible have in mind of expenditure in Indonesia. in consequence digital almighty dollar or cryptocurrency is advised an asset assets property not a expenditure artifact.

In Indonesia, regulations regarding cryptocurrency are still in the development stage. The Commodity Futures Trading Supervisory Agency (BAPPEBTI) has issued many modifications with reference to crypto assets property trading. principle is an far-reaching antioxidant as a justification for digital up-to-dateness transactions, for this generalization BAPPEBTI set forth Bappebti principle No. 7 of 2020 in reference to deciding the information of Crypto assets property that buoy Be Traded on the strong-

arm Crypto assets property Market. Basically, resource from cryptocurrency negotiations in Indonesia is paragraph to determine in conformation with applicative determine provisions. Cryptocurrency negotiations in Indonesia are paragraph to resource determine (PPh) clause 22 of 0. resource determine clause 22 is deducted as the crow flies when negotiations are carried elsewhere on exchangers or cryptocurrency trading rostra that are lawfully certified in Indonesia, much as Indodax and Tokocrypto. This resource determine is levied as belonging of the government's exertions to administer the cryptocurrency ecosystem and make certain that profits gross from digital assets property negotiations are monitored by the determine jurisdictions.

Apart from PPh Article 22, cryptocurrency transactions are also subject to Value Added Tax (VAT) of 0.11%. This VAT is applied to the transfer of crypto assets to other parties, either through buying and selling or exchanging. Physical Asset Traders (PFAK) are subject to a VAT rate of 0.11% of the transaction value for trading crypto assets. In the case of trading organizers who are not supervised by PFAK, the VAT rate on crypto asset trading is 0.22% of the transaction value. Apart from having asset transaction verification, mining services are subject to a VAT rate of 1.1% of the crypto asset conversion value. According to Article 16 paragraph (1) of Minister of Finance Regulation 68/PMK.03/2022 concerning Value Added Tax and Income Tax on Crypto Asset Trading Transactions, VAT includes the provision of crypto asset transaction verification services and/or management of crypto asset mining groups (also known as mining pools). Crypto asset miners are considered PKP, and the VAT is paid and deposited in a certain amount. If crypto asset miners receive crypto asset miner group management services or crypto asset transaction verification services, the amount of VAT that must be paid is 10% of the VAT rate multiplied by the value of the crypto assets they receive, including crypto assets received from the crypto asset system (block reward).

The Minister of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia issued regulations regarding taxes on trading of crypto commodity assets as outlined in the Regulation of the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia No. 68/PMK.03/2022 concerning Value Added Tax and Income Tax on Crypto Asset Trading Transactions. The enactment of these tax regulations has had its pros and cons. These regulations are applied in crypto exchange applications that are registered with BAPPEBTI. The existence of tax regulations set by the government is the first step for the crypto industry in Indonesia because the establishment of crypto taxes in Indonesia ensures that the Indonesian government is starting to be open to the crypto industry, there is legal certainty and tax certainty.

Figure 1: Tax Collection Scheme For Selling And Buying Crypto Assets

Cryptocurrency investors and traders in Indonesia are required to report profits obtained from cryptocurrency transactions in their Annual Income Tax Return (SPT Annual PPh). This ensures that all tax obligations related to digital asset transactions are fulfilled in accordance with applicable regulations. If there is a delay in paying tax, a fine will be imposed in accordance with applicable regulations. This fine aims to encourage taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations on time. Reporting income from cryptocurrency transactions is an integral part of investors' tax obligations in Indonesia. Investors are expected to keep accurate and detailed records of all their cryptocurrency transactions to facilitate proper reporting in their Annual Income Tax Returns. So that later all cryptocurrency transactions can be reported accurately and fulfill all tax obligations in accordance with applicable tax regulations.

The implementation of taxes on cryptocurrencies in Indonesia reflects the government's efforts to accommodate the development of digital assets while ensuring that the economic activities that occur remain within clear regulatory corridors. With a deep understanding of cryptocurrencies and the associated tax obligations, market players can make wise and sustainable decisions in exploiting the potential offered by these digital currencies in Indonesia and around the world. Considering that Indonesia is a sovereign state with a the greater part moslem population, issuing a fatwa from the body is extremely far-reaching so that it does not consideration discombobulation surrounded by the agreement as cryptocurrency users. For this reason, the governmental shariah Council-Indonesian bodies conference (DSN-MUI) buoy publication a fatwa that buoy accommodate a course of action or answer. with reference to a disputed point that continues in sovereign state so that it does not consideration discombobulation surrounded by Muslims in the application of cryptocurrency.

From a sharia perspective, there is a debate approximately the continuance of effective currencies. The Turkish government's churchgoing jurisdictions and Egypt's impressive Mufti chalk up alleged that effective currencies are haram or forbidden. on the other hand the Islamic institution of southbound Africa's fatwa centerfield has allowed effective up-to-dateness in trading. Cryptocurrency has been the

fundamental deed of Blockchain application and its potentiality is not constricted to expenditure organized whole alone. decentralised utilizations created buoy fundamentally consequence spaces of get-up-and-go much as economics, body of knowledge education, art, sophistication and others. (Shovkhalov & Idrisov, 2021) in the meantime in the conception of the MUI, it confesses that with reference to the legality of the application of cryptocurrency and the collection of its application in patronage negotiations according to Islamic law, thither are all the more pros and cons (khilafiyah) surrounded by economical professionals and ulama. In 2017 the asian bodies conference so issued a fatwa with reference to the application of Digital Electronic almighty dollar videlicet in DSN-MUI No. 116 of 2017 in reference to shariah electronic almighty dollar.

In the 7th Ulama Ijtima of the Fatwa Commission of the Indonesian Ulema Council which was held in November 2021 in Jakarta, the asian bodies conference so accepted the collection with reference to the application of Cryptocurrency in Indonesia, videlicet that the application of cryptocurrency in the configuration of up-to-dateness is haram, thanks to it have in it constituents of Gharar and Dharar. Cryptocurrencies furthermore contravene with collection character 7 of 2011 and deposit Indonesia principle character 17 of 2015 if they are euphemistic pre-owned as currency. The application of cryptocurrency as a digital assets property is haram when traded, thanks to it have in it constituents of Gharar, Dharar, and Qimar. So it does not satisfy the qualifications of Sil'ah according to the Shari'a, namely; be required to chalk up a strong-arm form, the expenditure be required to be recognized certainly, chalk up ownership rights so that it buoy be bimanual on top of to the buyer. Cryptocurrency is a commodity/asset that qualifies as sil'ah and has and has crystallise advantages that are lawfully authentic for purchasing and marketing.

B. Formulation of the Problem

1. What are the Principles of Cryptocurrency Tax Regulations in Indonesia?
2. How is Qanun Syari'ah applied to digital cryptocurrency investment?
3. What are the Benefits and Disadvantages of Cryptocurrency According to Qanun Syari'ah Views?

C. RESEARCH METHODS

Literature review or literature review is a method euphemistic pre-owned in evaluation research. A creative writings another look or what buoy be titled a creative writings contemplate is a classification of collections solicitation procedure that is carried elsewhere nailed down a another look contemplate of creative writings reports, notations and publications related the disputed point subject-matter continuance discussed. A creative writings another look is an far-reaching transaction subsequently deciding a evaluation topic, videlicet by conducting a hypothetical contemplate that is related the evaluation subject-matter (Nazir, 2018).

The research method in this study uses a normative juridic evaluation method, victimisationing the undermentioned evaluation drawing near contingency approach. The drawing near is carried elsewhere by conducting a contemplate of containers accompanying to the publication at participation. In this case, we take several examples of phenomenal cases which ultimately led to public interest in following this, supported by ease of transactions and very advanced and adequate technological

developments. However, the government has not yet made regulations regarding this matter so it needs to be studied and seen from the element of legal certainty.

The data collection technique used is library research. Data obtained during the evaluation testament be analysed victimisationing qualitative descriptive methods. The communicator cut down on the collections that has been obtained during the evaluation by pigeonholing and selecting collections that is substantial to the evaluation study. The coterminous stagecoach is that the investigator systematizes the collections that has been classified antecedently, and finally the researcher verifies or draws conclusions (Nugrahani & Hum, 2014).

D. DISCUSSION

1. Principles of Cryptocurrency Tax Regulations in Indonesia

a. Cryptocurrency Tax Regulations in Indonesia

Through UU no. 7 of 2021 Regarding Harmonization of Tax Regulations, the government determines crypto assets to be tax objects and subject to VAT and PPh taxes. This is stated in the implementing regulations of the Income Tax Law through Minister of Finance Regulation No. 68/PMK.03/2022 concerning Value Added Tax (VAT) and Income Tax (PPh) on Crypto Asset Trading Transactions.

Table 1: Basic Settings

No	Transaksi	Pemungut Pajak	Tarif Pajak	Administrasi Pemungutan
1	Perdagangan aset kripto: • Jual beli aset kripto dg uang fiat; dan • Tukar-menukar aset kripto (swab) • Pertukaran aset kripto dengan barang/jasa (pemindahan aset kripto ke akun lainnya)	PPN Platform exchanger (PFAK) sebagai pihak lain pemungut PPN (Ps 32A UU HPP) PPh Platform exchanger (PFAK) sebagai pihak lain pemungut PPN (tidak termasuk PPMSE yang hanya menyediakan jasa layanan dompet elektronik/e-wallet)	PPN: • 0,11% PPN dari nilai aset kripto (terdaftar di Bappepti) • 0,22% PPN dari nilai aset kripto (tidak terdaftar di Bappepti) PPh: • 0,1% PPh 22 Final dari nilai aset kripto (terdaftar di Bappepti) • 0,2% PPh 22 Final dr nilai aset kripto (tidak terdaftar di Bappepti)	• pemungut pajak lapor pemungutan PPN dalam SPT Masa Put 1107 dan PPh 22 dalam SPT Masa PPh Unifikasi • Penjual sbg PKP lapor SPT Masa PPN (kolom penyerahan yg PPN-nya dipungut oleh Pemungut PPN) • Bukti transaksi yang dibuat oleh platform exchanger/PFAK dapat sebagai: a. bukti pungut PPN dan PPh 22 (Dokumen yang Dipersamakan dengan Bukti Pematongan/Pemungutan Unifikasi) oleh platform exchanger; dan b. FP bagi penjual yang PKP

Source: www.pajak.go.id

Imposition of crypto tax on crypto asset trading through the appointment of a third party as VAT collector on crypto asset trading. VAT and crypto VAT collectors are Trade Organizers via Electronic Systems (PPMSE), both domestically and abroad. Trade organizers via electronic systems or PPMSE are taxpayers who have been confirmed as assessable Entrepreneurs (PKP). Except that, PPMSE be required to furthermore gather together PPh clause 22 on crypto assets property transactions. VAT on the preparation of crypto assets property development check utilities and/or crypto assets property mineworker accumulation administration utilities is self-collected by Crypto assets property Miners (miners) who chalk up been habitual as PKP.

Figure 2

b. Cryptocurrency Tax VAT and PPH Collection Scheme

The specific amount of VAT on the provision of crypto assets property development check utilities and/or crypto assets property mineworker accumulation administration utilities by crypto assets property miners is 11% of the VAT proportion multiplied by the price of the crypto assets property conventional by crypto assets property miners, including crypto assets property conventional from crypto assets property transaction. Crypto VAT collectors or crypto VAT taxes are Trade Operators via Electronic Systems (PPMSE), both domestic and overseas. Trade organizers via electronic systems or PPMSE are taxpayers who have been confirmed as Taxable Entrepreneurs (PKP). Apart from that, PPMSE must also collect PPh Article 22 on crypto asset transactions. As explained above, VAT on the provision of crypto assets property development check utilities and/or crypto assets property mineworker accumulation administration utilities is self-collected by Crypto assets property Miners (miners) who chalk up been habitual as PKP.

Based on Minister of Finance Regulation (PMK) Number 68 of 2022 concerning VAT and PPh on Crypto Asset Trading Transactions, the government sets rates for Value Added Tax (VAT) and Income Tax (PPh) on crypto transactions. The enforcement of determine on crypto assets property testament be remodelled efficacious on hawthorn 1, 2022. The administration inflicts taxes on crypto assets property of progression not without reason. judgement from the modifications of the artifact time to come Trading administrative superintendence (Bappebti), it interprets that crypto assets property are commodities and not a spiritualist of exchange. in consequence crypto assets property are categorized as unperceivable assessable artifacts which buoy be paragraph to expenditure Added determine (VAT). Crypto assets property themselves are digital assets property that are in the blockchain system. The blockchain transaction is a application that is euphemistic pre-owned as a storage transaction or collections deposit that is digitally machine-accessible with cryptography. illustrations of crypto assets property much as Bitcoin, Ethereum, Binance Coin, Theter, and others. Each of these assets property buoy be traded and

transacted globally every day after day for 24 hours. The substitution proportion of each assets property is mean business by the distribute and requirement of trading marketplace participators.

c. Cryptocurrency Tax Collection Rules in Indonesia

Article 17 paragraph (3) PMK 68/2022, in terms of compensation received by crypto asset miners for handing over crypto assets in connection with transaction verification services and/or management services for groups of crypto asset miners (mining pools) in the form of:

- 1) Fiat currency other than rupiah currency, the fiat currency is reborn into rupiah up-to-dateness supported on the substitution proportion mean business by the diplomatic negotiations of money management (Tax proportion or sacred calling of money management substitution Rate).
- 2) These crypto assets are converted into rupiah up-to-dateness supported on: The expenditure establish by the time to come substitution that carries elsewhere crypto assets property trading, or supported on the expenditure in the transaction owned by crypto assets property miners, which is mean business systematically.

All income must be taxed, including income originating from buying and selling activities. In Indonesia, bitcoin has legal status for buying and selling, but only as a digital asset commodity, not as a legal means of payment. If a profit occurs when making a transaction with bitcoin, then the individual or business entity that makes the profit must be taxed. If the perpetrator is an individual, he will be categorized as an individual taxpayer. Activities carried out personally in the form of trading (buying and selling activities in a short time) will be subject to Final Income Tax based on PP No.23 of 2018 at a rate of 0.5% without minimum provisions with a maximum turnover of IDR 4.8 billion per year. When turnover exceeds the maximum provisions, a progressive rate of 5% to 30% will be charged. If the profit is based on the name of the company, then the tax amount is adjusted to the corporate income tax rate.

In PMK Number 68 of 2022, it is explained that crypto assets are unperceivable commodities in the configuration of digital assets property victimisation cryptography, noblewoman to noblewoman networks, and apportioned ledgers to administer the introduction of contemporary units, bear witness to transactions, and unthreatened negotiations without interference from over-the-counter parties. Crypto assets property trading in Indonesia is underneath the protections of the artifact time to come Trading administrative superintendence (Bappebti). The arranger of crypto assets property trading in Indonesia is the strong-arm Crypto assets property merchandiser (PFAK). A strong-arm Crypto assets property merchandiser is a congregation who has obtained commendation from an accredited authoritative in conformation with the regulations and modifications governing artifact time to come trading, to accomplish crypto assets property negotiations either on behalf of themselves/and/or facilitating negotiations of Crypto assets property salespersons or Crypto assets property purchasers.

d. Imposition of Cryptocurrency Asset Tax in Indonesia

Tax regulations for cryptocurrency trading are issued by the Republic of Indonesia Financial Metrics Regulation number 63/PMK.03/2022, where these negotiations are paragraph to expenditure Added determine and resource Tax. It is furthermore backhand that crypto assets property are commodities and are tangibles of

expenditure added determine as thermostated in clause 4 content (1) of collection character 8 of 1983, in reference to expenditure Added determine on artifacts and utilities and sellings determine on sumptuousness Goods, and chalk up been virtually freshly revised by collection character 7 of 1983. 2021 in reference to harmony of determine Regulations. If the salesperson is a PKP, the marketing of crypto assets property be required to constitute a determine account and be held electronically, patch stimulation determine cannot be credited. resource from crypto assets property trading is supplementary economical potentiality conventional by taxpayers from Indonesia and from elsewhere Indonesia which is the phenomenon of resource determine as thermostated in clause 4 content (1) of collection character 7 of 1983, in reference to resource Tax, and has been antepenultimate revised with collection character 7 of 2021 in reference to harmony of Tax Regulations.

Income from all types of crypto assets in the form of; a) transactions with payments in fiat currency, b) exchange between crypto assets, c) crypto asset transactions other than transactions as stated in letters a and b. Under the conventional regulations currently in force, income tax imposed on permanent business entities still has the requirement that the entity has a building or office located in Indonesia. In fact, there are quite a few entities or forms of business that operate digitally and do not have offices in the form of physical buildings. It may indeed be a trivial matter for business practice. However, in the tax sector, this requires further study so that digital business actors also continue to carry out tax obligations from the business activities they carry out. Not a few digital business actors make mistakes in carrying out their tax obligations or even do not carry out their tax obligations for the reason that they do not know the applicable regulations.

The VAT rates imposed on crypto asset trading consist of 2 rates. The first rate is 1% (one percent) of the VAT rate multiplied by the crypto asset transaction value. This rate applies if the Trading Operator via an Electronic System is a Physical Crypto Asset Trader. The second rate is 2% (two percent) of the VAT rate multiplied by the transaction value in the event that the Trading Operator via an Electronic System is not a Physical Crypto Asset Trader. Apart from these two rates, crypto trading is also subject to Income Tax (PPh) Article 22 which is levied on sellers organizing Trading via Electronic Systems. The PPh rate is 0.1%. Trade Operators via Electronic Systems are required to provide proof of VAT collection payable in the form of a document equivalent to Unification Withholding/Collection Receipt. The way to impose tax on crypto asset trading is by appointing a third party as a VAT collector, namely the organizer of Trading Through Electronic Systems (PPMSE) both domestically and abroad.

Indonesia is ranked number 4 with the largest number of crypto asset investors in the world. Apart from that, based on a report from the Ministry of Trade, it is stated that the value of crypto asset transactions in 2020 reached IDR 64.9 trillion and increased to IDR 859.4 trillion in 2021. Crypto asset trading transactions in the period January to February 2022 were recorded at IDR 83.3 trillion. The imposition of VAT on crypto assets can be interpreted as a form of recognition of the legality of crypto asset trading. Apart from that, the implementation of VAT on crypto assets will certainly increase state income. This is supported by the number of crypto asset investors being higher than the capital market. It is hoped that the implementation of tax levies on crypto assets will run transparently and be able to make a positive contribution to the economy.

2. Application of Sharia Qanun to Cryptocurrency Digital Asset Investment

In Islamic economics and Islamic financial institutions, etymologically almighty dollar or literary draw nigh from the confabulation al-naqdu, videlicet cash. The confabulation nuqud is not constitute in the quran and Hadith, thanks to Arabs customarily do not application nuqud to denote price. They application the confabulation commotion to distinguish up-to-dateness make-believe of gilded and the confabulation dirham to distinguish a spiritualist of substitution make-believe of silver. This cryptocurrency is a up-to-dateness that is not thermostated by the administration and is not an authoritative up-to-dateness as a have in mind of payment. The conceptualization of Bitcoin itself has the assistance of self-determined privacy, which acknowledges each characteristic purchaser to unfeignedly chalk up full-of-the-moon hegemony on top of their ownership, does not ride the established banking system, and does not hurting for interference from whatever superintendence or institution. Electronic almighty dollar buoy be aforementioned to be a permissible have in mind of expenditure if it come across the requirements, videlicet that it is circulated supported on the proportion of almighty dollar deposited in rupiah, so that if these criteria are met and nailed down complementary agreement, the almighty dollar that testament circularise buoy be euphemistic pre-owned by the universal (Chaira et al., 2021).

Different views were also expressed by the Indonesian Ulema Council, where thither were severals pros and cons surrounded by asian body with reference to the permissible prominence of bitcoin itself, on the other hand in the 7th body Ijtima, Fatwa commissioning of the asian bodies conference which was held in November 2021, thither was a give-and-take approximately cryptocurrency collection and produced 3 far-reaching conclusions with reference to this matter, including (1) The application of cryptocurrency as a permissible up-to-dateness is haram, thanks to it have in it gharar, dharar and is obstinate to collection character 7 of 2011 and deposit Indonesia modifications (2) Cryptocurrency as a digital commodity/asset is valetudinarian bought and oversubscribed thanks to it have in it gharar, dharar, qimar and does not accommodate the qualifications of sil'ah on the authority of syar'i, namely, has a strong-arm form, has value, the faultless proportion is known, dimethyl ketone rights and buoy be bimanual on top of to the purchaser (3) Cryptocurrency as a commodity/asset which fulfills the qualifications as sil'ah and has an implicit and has crystallise advantages which are lawfully authentic purchasable and purchase. So supported on the Ijtima, the application of cryptocurrency as up-to-dateness is haram, thanks to it have in it gharar and dharar.

From the perspective of Islamic law and Islamic financial institutions, Bitcoin currency is issued. Bitcoin is not by oneself assessed in designations of form, on the other hand is assessed in designations of its advantages and uses. judgement from the disadvantageous aspect, Bitcoin purchasing and marketing negotiations are not permissible if contemplation (maysir) take place thither is an antioxidant of gaming to try one's luck, as a have in mind of betting, on the other hand each the misfortune and advantages ride the businessman and application of the Bitcoin itself. The MUI (Indonesian bodies Council) is all the more conducting extremely studies on Bitcoin, and has not issued an authoritative fatwa with reference to Bitcoin collection thanks to thither are all the more dissimilarities surrounded by MUI ulama, any of whom chalk up prohibited it and any chalk up not all the more mean business a trustworthy situation.

3. Benefits and Disadvantages of Cryptocurrency According to the View of the Implementation of Sharia Qanun

In fact, there is a lot of potential that buoy determination in the emergence of Cryptocurrency itself, turn from the upper hand informality of transactions, and all the more disadvantages. in reality, in every muamalat development that fix up with provision advantages to the social gathering involved, individual of them buoy carry through a benefit. on the other hand subsequently reviewing extremely with reference to the application of Cryptocurrency as digital currency, exceptionally when implementation on-line transactions, it rotates elsewhere that it have in it severals constituents of harm. This have in mind that thither are a collection of jeopardies that buoy be caused by the continuance of Cryptocurrency and it buoy be disadvantageous to its users, so this participation is not in conformation with the refreshments of the shariah taught by Islamic churchgoing teachings, namely, muamalat negotiations that consideration misfortune should be abandoned, according to what is explicit in many verses of the quran (Masruron, 2021).

This basic principle is the main basis for every collection stipulated in Islamic sharia. in consequence each configurations of goodness and benediction be required to carry forward to be pursued, patch each configurations of madharat and mafsadat be required to be avoided. So, to keep away from any of the misfortune that buoy originate from the participation of digital almighty dollar (Cryptocurrency), we should rate a circumspect mental state exceptionally in victimisation things. The expression that is appropriated into considerateness is the good fortune sides flanks which is in a superior way than the benefits, both when euphemistic pre-owned as a have in mind of expenditure and as a development tool.

The application of Cryptocurrency as a have in mind of expenditure transactions, exceptionally in on-line pecuniary transactions, is advised syubhāt, and something that is syubhāt should be abandoned, thanks to it does not institute advantages and at the corresponding continuance intervals the destination of Islamic law, videlicet the benediction of each general public (Darmawansyah et al., 2021). So, to answer various legal rules that are not appropriate, individual of them is mean business nailed down the refreshments contained in the Qur'an and As-Sunnah. In Indonesia, the established up-to-dateness is the Rupiah, and with affection to each configurations of application of Cryptocurrency as a development belonging or all the more a commodity, the expression of responsibility bes a member of to each characteristic or agreement itself. It is prerogative that the administration does not proscribe the circuit of digital almighty dollar on the other hand what be in want of to be a word to the wise to the agreement or purchasers themselves is that each jeopardies with reference to application accompanying to safe keeping are the responsibility of the users. The administration does not participate in it, so if at whatever continuance persona non grata inanimate object come to pass or deplorable undertakings accompanying to the circuit and application of Cryptocurrency, it is crystallise that the administration testament not appropriate belonging thanks to it is not inside its administration.

E. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion in the previous chapter, it can be concluded as follows:

1. The conclusion from this research is that at a distance from continuance a development tool, crypto is furthermore extensively universal with the universal as an investment. individual expression of taxation imposed on crypto assets property is expenditure Added determine (VAT) and PPh. On crypto assets property trading, a trustworthy proportion of VAT or examination VAT is levied at a proportion of 0. 11 pct of the development expenditure if the commerce arranger is a strong-arm Crypto assets property merchandiser (PFAK) and 0. 22 pct if it is not a PFAK.
2. Views of Islamic economic law and Sharia Qanun So several discoveries buoy be outlined, including: As a digital pecuniary development system, cryptocurrency fundamentally put into practice to some degree contemporary technology, the individualism of its legality all the more be in want of to be premeditated in bounteous depth, on the other hand it is not a configuration of violation. In Indonesia itself, the administration has not appropriated a trustworthy department on the continuance of cryptocurrency, so general public are all the more allowed to application it. on the other hand financing in cryptocurrency carries a extremely high-pitched jeopardy thanks to its expenditure buoy rise or dip circle drastically and erratically.

Bibliography

- 1) Afrizal, Afrizal; Marliyah, M. (2021). psychoanalysis of Cryptocurrency (Currency, Legal, economical and shariah Perspectives). Journal of Management and Business Economics, Vol. 22, no. 2, 13–41.
- 2) Basson, R. (2020). An psychoanalysis of emanations relating to the taxation of cryptocurrencies as pecuniary implements. Journal of Economic and Financial Sciences, 13. <https://doi.org/10.4102/jef.v13i1.487>.
- 3) Chaira, CN, Furqani, H., & Amanatillah, D. (2021). The conceptualization of up-to-dateness in Islamic Economics (Analysis of Bitcoin as a effective Currency). SHARIA ECOBIS, 3(2), 34-44.
- 4) Darmawansyah, TT, Firdaus, F., & Aguspriyani, Y. (2021). Mashlahah and Mafsadah Cryptocurrency as Official State Currency. MUAMALATUNA, 13(2), 83-105.
- 5) Irma, Dasih, et al. (2021). " The looked toward of Cryptocurrency Legality in Indonesia. " fish wrapper of Economics and patronage characters, vol. 1, no. 1.
- 6) *Mardiasmo*. (2016). Latest Edition of Taxation 2016. Publisher: Andi Offset. Yogyakarta.
- 7) Masruron, M. (2021). Islamic collection another look of Bitcoin negotiations from the vantage point of graeco-roman and present-day Fiqh professors. TAFALQUH: Journal of Sharia Economic Law and Ahwal Syahsiyah, 6(1), 52-65.
- 8) *Nazir, Moh.* (2018). Research methods. Bogor: Ghalia Indonesia.
- 9) *Nugrahani, F., & Hum, M.* (2014). Qualitative research methods. Solo: Chakra. Books.
- 10) Syamsiah, NO (2017). "Contemplate of Cryptocurrency as a have in mind of expenditure in Indonesia". Indonesia Journal on Networking and safe keeping, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2311/ijns.v6i1.1449>. P.53-61.
- 11) *Syaugoti, R., & Ghozali, M.* (2018). transaction psychoanalysis of shariah pecuniary originations and established pecuniary originations. Iqtishaduna Journal, 14(1), 15-21.